

STRENGTH REDUCTION OF GRP COMPOSITES EXPOSED TO HIGH TEMPERATURE MARINE ENVIRONMENTS

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SUMMARY: A programme of tests has been conducted to characterise the strength reduction of three GRP composites as a function of temperature and testing environment. The materials were two E-glass reinforced epoxies and E-glass reinforced phenolic. The testing environments were sea water and crude oil condensate at temperatures from ambient to 150°C. Results are presented for the strength of the three materials as a function of temperature in fibre and resin dominated failure modes when tested dry and saturated in water and oil respectively.

- Fibre dominated strength is insensitive to high temperatures.
- Resin dominated strength of epoxy based materials is greatly reduced at high temperatures.
- Resin dominated strength of the phenolic based material is reduced only slightly at high temperatures, but its low temperature strength is poor.
- Sea water saturation greatly exacerbates the strength reduction of all the materials tested. Oil has little effect.

KEYWORDS: GRP, FRP, tensile strength, tensile testing, environmental testing, sea water, marine environment, offshore environment

INTRODUCTION

Composite materials are progressively gaining acceptance for use in offshore applications where their perceived virtues of low weight and good corrosion resistance are much sought after by designers and operators. Glass fibre reinforced plastics (GRP) in particular have won widespread acceptance in nonstructural applications, including fire water piping, decking and cable trays. There is however considerable interest in the use of GRP of various types in more demanding applications offshore. Such new applications involve using the material in contact with aggressive process fluids at elevated temperatures. Examples of applications under consideration include separator vessels (where various hydrocarbons and water are present at 70-80°C, with possible excursions above 100°C), subsea flowlines and, perhaps the most demanding application, down hole tubing and drill stream parts. Although the temperatures involved in the most demanding down hole applications are too high to permit the use of organic matrix composites, there is a range of applications where the temperatures are somewhat lower and GRP offers significant potential advantages.

To help assess the suitability of GRP in these demanding offshore applications, a programme of tests has been carried out to measure the strength of three candidate materials as a function of temperature in typical operating environments. This is the work described in this paper.

The effects of environment on GRP

Most tests carried out to date to determine the response of composite materials to environmental degradation have been carried out at ambient temperature. However, it is known that elevated temperature softens most resins, particularly above the glass transition temperature (T_G) [1]. This reduces the interlaminar shear strength and so the strength of the composite when it is loaded such that the fibres are not in pure tension. The glass fibres are not susceptible to corrosion unless the absorbed water is acidic, in which case the effect can be dramatic [2].

The flexural strength of glass/polyester laminates and glass/epoxy pipes aged in sea water at ambient temperature have been shown to reduce by up to 20% within a year [3]. Absorbed water is known to act as a plasticiser [4], reducing T_G , and has been shown to reduce the strength and modulus of amine cured epoxies [1]. It can thus be expected to exacerbate this loss of properties at high temperatures.

The presence of oil is believed to have little effect on fibre composites. Polyester/glass laminates exposed to dehydrated oil at temperatures up to 90°C for 90 days have been shown to behave in the same way as unexposed laminates [5].

EXPERIMENTAL DETAILS

Test Programme

The programme of tensile tests was undertaken on coupon specimens of three different GRP materials at elevated temperatures in two marine environments: natural sea water and oil condensate. For comparison, the materials were also tested in the normal laboratory environment (air at ambient humidity) and at ambient temperature in the test environments.

The tensile tests were carried out on specimens that had previously been saturated in the test environment. To ensure that the specimens were truly saturated, a series of absorption tests was first carried out on each material in each environment to determine the time required to reach saturation.

Tensile tests were carried out on coupon specimens with the fibre reinforcement laid in two different directions: 0/90° and ±45° with respect to the direction of loading. With the fibres oriented at 0/90° approximately half of the fibres were loaded axially and so the failure was controlled by the strength of the fibres (fibre dominated failure mode). With the ±45° oriented fibres, the failure was largely controlled by the strength of the resin matrix (resin dominated failure mode).

Tensile tests were carried out under quasi-static axial loading conditions with the specimen at constant temperature and immersed in the test environment.

Figure 1: Schematic representation of the environmental tensile testing chamber

The tensile tests were carried out in the specially developed environmental tensile testing chamber shown schematically in Figure 1, described fully in [6]. Briefly, it consists of a tensile testing machine (loading frame, hydraulic actuator, load cell and specimen grips) contained within a pressure vessel. This facility made possible the testing of specimens whilst immersed in liquids at high temperatures above the normal boiling point. Boiling was inhibited by allowing the pressure to rise as the temperature increased.

A particular feature of the testing chamber is the thermally defined gauge length. The specimen is heated to the test temperature only in a short region near its mid-length. The ends of the specimen remain relatively cool. Since the material is weakened at elevated temperatures, this differential heating ensures that the specimens always fail in the gauge length and not at the entrance to the grips. This arrangement eliminates the need for special specimen geometry.

Test Environments

Natural Sea Water. Sea water was taken directly from the North Sea at the coast near Newcastle upon Tyne.

Oil Condensate. Samples of crude oil, modified only by flashing off the light fractions, were supplied by Philips Petroleum. The samples supplied were typical of light crudes.

MATERIALS

Resin Matrix Materials. Three generic resin types were chosen for this work, representing the materials of greatest interest to the offshore community. These were:

- aromatic amine (MDA) cured epoxy,

- cycloaliphatic amine (IPD) cured epoxy, and
- acid-cured phenolic.

These resins are all capable of being processed into GRP components by liquid fabrication methods such as contact moulding and filament winding.

The epoxy resins were of the type widely employed in the fabrication of GRP pipework. The aromatic amine curing agent, MDA, is known to give resins with the higher T_G and generally good high temperature properties. Unfortunately there are some health and safety concerns about the carcinogenicity of this material. This has led to its replacement in Europe, for some applications, by the cycloaliphatic amine curing agent IPD which is less toxic. IPD is known to give resins with a somewhat lower T_G and hence inferior high temperature properties. Clarification of the relative thermal performance of composites based on these two key thermosetting resins in liquid environments was the main reason for their inclusion in the test programme.

The epoxy resins used for the fabrication of coupon samples were of the same composition used for the commercial manufacture of GRP pipes. The epoxy component was supplied by Shell Chemicals (Epikote 827). The IPD curing agent was Vestamin IPD, supplied by Hüls and the MDA curing agent was Ancamine 1692, supplied by Anchor Chemicals (Air Products). Both agents were used in the proportion recommended by the manufacturer of the epoxy resin.

The phenolic resin samples were fabricated from the acid-cured liquid phenolic resin, Cellobond J2042L, supplied by BP. They were cured by the addition of the manufacturers' recommended quantity of strong acid catalyst, Phencat 382.

Glass Reinforcement Material. The reinforcement used throughout was epoxy and phenolic compatible E-glass woven rovings (600gm/m^2), supplied by Owens Corning Fibreglass.

COUPON SPECIMEN MANUFACTURE

The specimens were made in-house by contact moulding, with dove-tail ends for mounting in purpose-designed matching grips of the tensile testing machine. This technique ensured a consistent fibre volume fraction from sample to sample and from sheet to sheet. The mould included chamfered ends in which the dove-tails were built up by placing extra strips of glass between the normal fibre layers. The mould was used to make flat sheet laminate of $500 \times 500\text{mm}$, two sides of which had a 50mm wide dove-tail with an included angle of 10° . This sheet was then cut into strips approximately 23mm wide using a fine tooth band saw. These strips were then milled down to 21mm in order to minimise damage to the edges. The final specimen dimensions were 600mm long \times 21mm wide \times $\approx 3.5\text{mm}$ thick.

ABSORPTION TEST PROCEDURE

Samples 60mm and 100mm long were cut from the coupon specimens. The samples were weighed initially and then immersed in the test liquids (sea water and oil condensate) at 100°C . They were removed from the environment at intervals and reweighed. This procedure was repeated until the rate of increase in mass had reduced to a level that indicated that effective saturation had been achieved.

TENSILE TEST PROCEDURE

Dry Tests. Specimens of the three material systems investigated were tested to failure at various temperatures in air (i.e. in the absence of any aggressive environment). The results of these tests were used as a baseline against which the subsequent tests on specimens subjected to conditioning in the test environments could be compared.

Saturated Water Tests. Prior to testing, specimens were conditioned in the test environment for a period sufficient to ensure saturation (as determined in the absorption tests described above). Each specimen was loaded into the test rig and immersed in the environment as quickly as possible after removal from the conditioning chamber. The heater was switched on and, as soon as the gauge length had settled at the test temperature, the specimen was loaded quasi-statically to failure. Load and temperature were monitored and recorded for subsequent analysis.

Saturated Condensate Tests. The testing procedure was the same as that for saturated water testing, using the appropriate conditioning time to ensure saturation of the specimens prior to testing.

RESULTS

Absorption Tests

Sea Water Absorption. The water absorption data for coupon tests of the three materials are given in Table 1. The water uptake was in all cases quite low. The epoxies show a 1-2% increase in mass due to water absorption at saturation and the phenolic, though slightly higher, was still only 2.2%.

Table 1: Saturation of materials in sea water at 100°C

Resin system	Time to saturation	Added mass at saturation
MDA Epoxy	6 days	1.8%
IPD epoxy	3 days	1.1%
Phenolic	5 days	2.3%

It was found that the expected high initial rates of absorption varied between materials, but that in all cases the rate of absorption quickly fell. In the case of the IPD epoxy and phenolic systems there was little further uptake after two days immersion. With the MDA cured epoxy the time to effective saturation was five days.

Oil Condensate Absorption. As shown in Table 2, there was very little absorption of oil into the epoxy materials. In the case of the phenolic resin composite, which is known to form voids in the matrix, it is believed that the increased mass is due to these voids being filled rather than any interaction with the fibre or matrix materials.

Table 2: Saturation of materials in crude oil condensate at 100°C

Resin system	Time to saturation	Added mass at saturation
MDA Epoxy	5 days	<0.1
IPD epoxy	2 days	<0.1
Phenolic	2 days	1.4

TENSILE TESTS

Dry Tests. The results for the matrix dominated $\pm 45^\circ$ coupon tests (Figure 2) show that in all cases the matrix material is strongly dependent on temperature. At ambient temperature, the aromatic amine (MDA) cured epoxy was the strongest of the three materials tested with a tensile strength of 90MPa. This strength is only slightly reduced at temperatures up to 60°C, but is reduced by 50% to 45MPa at about 110°C and to only 12MPa at 120°C. The aliphatic amine (IPD) cured epoxy system was weaker than the aromatic at all temperatures and followed a similar curve. The tensile strength at ambient temperature was around 80 MPa, began to drop at only 40°C and was reduced to 50% of its initial strength (40 MPa) at 80°C.

Figure 2: $\pm 45^\circ$ specimens tested dry

At low temperatures the phenolic based material is weaker in the matrix dominated mode than either of the epoxy materials, but it is less affected by temperature than the epoxies due to its high T_G . Even at a temperature of 160°C the strength of the phenolic material was reduced by only 30% to 42MPa. Its tensile strength becomes greater than that of the MDA cured epoxy material (the stronger of the two epoxies) at about 100°C.

The results of the 0/90° dry tests (Figure 3) show that the specimens were only marginally affected by an increase in temperature. This is to be expected in this fibre dominated mode since the E-glass is not greatly affected by moderate temperatures. All three materials show a reduction in strength of approximately of 8% over the range from ambient to 160°C.

Figure 3: 0/90° specimens tested dry

Sea Water Tests. Figures 4-6 show the results of tensile tests carried out at various temperatures on coupon specimens using the three resin systems in the matrix dominated $\pm 45^\circ$ mode. In all cases the specimens were saturated in sea water prior to testing and the tests were conducted with the specimens in contact with the water. As may be seen, all three materials showed a reduction in strength due to the environment, but this effect was most pronounced in the two epoxy materials.

Figure 4: strength reduction in $\pm 45^\circ$ MDA cured epoxy specimens due to sea water saturation

The results for the aromatic amine (MDA) cured epoxy material in Figure 4 show that this material is only moderately affected by sea water at elevated temperatures. At ambient temperature, the strength of the saturated material is reduced by about 15% relative to the dry material. The strength reduces as a function of temperature similarly to the material in the dry state, being reduced by 50% to 40MPa at 100°C.

The results for the aliphatic amine (IPD) cured epoxy material shown in Figure 5 are more dramatic. Of the two epoxy systems tested, this is the more sensitive to even moderate temperatures in the dry state. When saturated with sea water, the material is slightly weakened even at ambient temperature. At 40°C its tensile strength is reduced significantly, at 50°C it is reduced to 50% of its ambient temperature value and at 60°C its strength is negligible.

As shown in Figure 6, the phenolic system was only marginally affected by the salt water ingress at moderate temperatures up to 80°C. Above this temperature the effect is more marked, with strength falling rapidly above 100°C.

Oil Tests. As shown in Figure 7, oil immersion has no significant effect on the strength of any of the composite systems tested. In each case the strength of the material as a function of temperature follows the curve obtained in the baseline “dry” tests. This is to be expected as the absorption tests described above indicate very little penetration of the oil into the material.

DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

The effect of temperature and environment has been tested on coupon specimens of three composite materials. These comprise E-glass woven mat in a matrix of MDA cured epoxy, IPD cured epoxy and phenolic respectively.

The time required to saturate coupon specimens of the three material types with sea water was established in a series of absorption tests at 100°C. In the same way, saturation times were established for oil penetration into the coupon specimens. It was found that in all cases the materials became saturated in five days or less. This information was used to establish the conditioning times for the specimens used subsequently in the environmental degradation tests.

Loading modes of the specimens were selected to test the materials subject to both resin and fibre dominated failure modes. This was done by preparing coupon specimens with the fibres oriented at ±45° and 0/90° to the loading axis respectively.

Figure 5: strength reduction in ±45° IPD epoxy cured specimens due to sea water saturation

Figure 6: strength reduction in ±45° phenolic specimens due to sea water saturation

Figure 7: strength reduction in ±45° phenolic specimens due to sea water saturation

In all cases, the strength of the coupon specimens was found to reduce as testing temperature increased. However, there was considerable variation between materials, both in terms of the rate of fall off of strength with temperature and in the absolute value of the strength at any given temperature.

When not subjected to a hostile environment, the 0/90° (fibre dominated) materials were all only slightly affected by increased temperature. However, the ±45° (resin dominated) epoxy based materials were strongly effected by increased temperature with strength greatly reduced. This is due to the softening of the resin, particularly close to and above the glass transition temperature (T_G).

When tested in the dry state, the ±45° IPD cured epoxy, which was the weaker of the two epoxy materials at room temperature, was also the more sensitive to temperature. By 80°C the strength had dropped from 80MPa to 35MPa, which might be considered the limit of integrity in the resin dominated failure mode. The ±45° MDA cured epoxy was also severely weakened at high temperatures, dropping from 90MPa to 35MPa at 110°C, which might also be considered the limit of integrity in the matrix dominated mode. The ±45° phenolic based material was considerably weaker than either of the epoxy systems at low temperature, but was shown to be much less sensitive to temperature. This is undoubtedly due to the high T_G of the material which prevents softening in the temperature range tested. The phenolic material was found to be the strongest of the three materials in this mode at temperatures above 100°C, retaining a strength greater than 40MPa at 160°C. On the same basis it can be considered to have easily retained its integrity up to this high temperature.

As an alternative to an absolute residual strength, rate of strength loss might be a useful criterion for upper temperature limit of integrity since this reflects the sensitivity to small temperature excursions. On the basis of an integrity limit of 1MPa/degree, the resin dominated integrity limits for dry MDA and IPD cured epoxy GRPs are 90°C and 60°C respectively. On the same basis dry phenolic GRP retains its integrity to above 160°C.

All three materials tested showed a marked reduction in strength at all temperatures due to salt water absorption. This effect is particularly marked in ±45° IPD cured epoxy coupon specimens, in which the strength is reduced to 35MPa at 50°C and becomes negligible above 60°C. The effect is rather less significant in ±45° MDA in which the temperature for 35MPa strength is reduced from 110°C to just over 100°C. However, for the ±45° phenolic coupon specimens, which are particularly good when tested dry, the strength starts to fall away rapidly at temperatures above 80°C and drops to 35MPa at 110°C, though the rate of strength reduction of 0.8MPa/degree at that temperature.

IPD cured epoxy GRP loses its strength very quickly at elevated temperatures under these conditions, reducing to 35MPa at only 50°C and reaching the 1MPa/degree integrity limit below 40°C. Clearly it is unsuited for use in contact with sea water at elevated temperatures. The MDA cured material is much better, retaining its integrity to 100°C and 90°C according to the 35MPa and 1MPa/degree criteria respectively.

Phenolic based GRP has excellent stability at moderate temperatures, with very little loss of strength below 80°C. Even at higher temperatures it retains good stability and reaches the 35MPa integrity limit at 115°C, before the 1MPa/degree limit. However, its poor strength at

ambient temperature means that it is still weaker than the MDA cured epoxy material below 90°C. Only above this temperature does it emerge as the best material of the three tested.

The integrity of phenolic based GRP at high temperatures when saturated in sea water is thus seen to be only slightly superior to that of a MDA epoxy material in terms of residual strength. However, the phenolic material does have the advantage of much better stability in that its strength is much less dependent on temperature changes at high temperatures. If the operating temperature is not well defined at the design stage this could well be significant.

It is evident that immersion in oil, at least in the form of condensate, has very little effect on the strength of GRP in any of the forms tested. For each material tested the data points for strength at a given temperature lie squarely on the curve for the equivalent dry tests. This is to be expected since the absorption tests indicated very little ingress of the oil into any of the composite materials investigated in this work.

CONCLUSIONS

1. A cost effective methodology has been developed for preparing and testing the strength of both coupon and pipe specimens of fibre reinforced composite materials at elevated temperatures in liquid environments.
2. Three materials have been tested: E-glass reinforcement in cycloaliphatic amine (IPD) cured epoxy, aromatic amine (MDA) cured epoxy and acid-cured phenolic.
3. The time required for effective sea water saturation at a temperature of 100°C has been established for each material. In all cases this is five days or less.
4. The effects of sea water saturation on strength have been quantified as a function of temperature for the three material systems.
5. In all the materials tested, strength is reduced only slightly at elevated temperatures in fibre dominated failure mode.
6. In matrix dominated failure mode, the strength of both epoxy based materials falls off rapidly at elevated temperatures. This effect occurs at lower temperature in IPD cured epoxy than MDA cured epoxy.
7. In matrix dominated failure mode, the strength of phenolic based GRP is less affected by high temperature. However, its strength is lower than epoxy materials at ambient temperature. It was found to be stronger than IPD/epoxy GRP above 60°C and stronger than MDA/epoxy GRP above 100°C. At all temperatures the phenolic based GRP was found to be less sensitive to temperature change than either of the epoxy based systems.
8. Sea water was found to be the most aggressive of the environments tested, reducing the strength of all the materials at all temperatures. The strength reduction due to sea water absorption was approximately independent of temperature in MDA/epoxy GRP, but increased with temperature in IPD/epoxy and phenolic GRPs.

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